

Mapping Annual Mean Values to Indicative Labels

In the Air Quality Stripes project we wanted to place absolute concentrations of particulate matter (PM2.5) in a clear and easy to understand context.

Existing Mapping Approaches

To do this concentration categories were mapped to indicative labels e.g. “Very Good”, “Fair”, “Moderate” ect. This approach is widely used for air quality communication, e.g.the UK Daily Air Quality Index (<https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/air-pollution/daq>), the European Air Quality Index(<https://airindex.eea.europa.eu/AQI/index.html>) or the National Air Quality Index in India (https://airquality.cpcb.gov.in/AQI_India/). But in these links, the mapping from concentration to indicative varies from country to country. In addition, these indices all use daily PM2.5 levels, but the historical air quality stripes considers annual mean values. Both daily and annual mean values are considered by the World Health Organisation (1) in their “interim target” values (see table).

	1	2	3	4	AQG
Annual Mean	35	25	10	5	5
Daily Mean	75	50	37.5	25	15

WHO Interim Target Levels for PM2.5 (1)

Mapping Approach Used

In our review of existing mapping approaches we found that there isn’t a single, well established mapping of annual mean PM2.5 concentrations that we could adopt. Instead we developed a mapping, inspired by the daily indices above, but suitable for annual mean values and tailored to the range of values found in cities around the globe.

Indicative Value	Very Good	Fair	Moderate	Poor	Very Poor	Extremely Poor
Annual Mean PM2.5 (ug m-3)	0 - 5	5 - 15	15 - 30	30 - 50	50 - 70	> 70

In the air quality stripes images the same mapping is used for all locations, so e.g. “Poor” in every city reflects the same band of PM2.5 concentrations.

(1) WHO global air quality guidelines. Particulate matter (PM2.5 and PM10), ozone, nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide and carbon monoxide. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2021. Licence: CC BYNC-SA 3.0 IGO, <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240034228>